

VIDYANKUR

**Journal of Philosophical
and Theological Studies**

January-June 2021

XXIII/1

Contents

Editorial: Reason and/or Religion -----	3
Khumtang Y Tikhir -----	6
Science and Religion Reconciled: A Close Look at God of Evolution	
Henry Jose -----	17
A Daring Approach in Bridging God and Darwin by Francis S. Collins in The Language of God	
Carmel Raj D. -----	29
Science and/vs Religion: What Do Scientists Really Think about Religion?	
Milton Nicholasrajan -----	44
Moving Towards One World: The Interaction of Science and Theology	
J. C. Paul Rohan -----	56
Religious Indifference and Lived Atheism: The 'Religious Pulse' of the World at Present	

Vidyankur: Journal of Philosophical and Theological Studies is a peer-reviewed interdisciplinary. A bi-annual published in January and July, the journal seeks to discern wisdom in our troubled times. Inspiring and brief academic articles beneficial to the educated audience are welcome. It attempts to foster personal integration through philosophical search, theological insights, scientific openness and social concern.

Editorial Board

Dr Kuruvilla Pandikattu Joseph, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 411014

Dr Ginish C. Baby, Christ University, Lavasa, Pune Dt

Dr Binoy Pichalakkattu, Loyola Institute of Peace and International Studies, Kochi

Dr Samuel Richmond, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology & Sciences, Allahabad

Dr Shiju Sam Varughese, Central University of Gujarat, Gandhinagar

Dr Shalini Chakranarayan, Assistant Professor, English Language Institute Member, Jazan University

Ms Gargi Mukherjee, Res Scholar, Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan

For additional Board Members, please visit <https://www.vidyankur.in/board-members>

Publisher: Dr Kuruvilla Pandikattu Joseph

Site: www.vidyankur.in

Email: [indianjournal\[at\]gmail.com](mailto:indianjournal[at]gmail.com)

ISSN: 2320-9429 CODEN: VJPTAK

OCLC: 233921404 LCCN: 2008306810

Printed at Kunal Offset Press, 499 Vartak Apartment, Narayan Peth, Shaniwar Peth, Pune, 411030

Published Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 411014, India

Editorial

Reason and/or Religion

Religious people facing life crises rely on emotion-regulation strategies that psychologists also use, a new study finds. They look for positive ways of thinking about hardship, a practice known to psychologists as ‘cognitive reappraisal.’ They also tend to have confidence in their ability to cope with difficulty, a trait called ‘coping self-efficacy.’ Both have been shown to reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, reports a study by the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (2021).

”It appears that religious people are making use of some of the same tools that psychologists have systematically identified as effective in increasing well-being and protecting against distress,” said Florin Dolcos, a professor of psychology, who led the study with psychology professor Sanda Dolcos and graduate student Kelly Hohl. “This suggests that science and religion are on the same page when it comes to coping with hardship,” he said.

Cite as: Pandikattu, Kuruville. (2019). Editorial: Reason and /for Religion. (Version 1.0) Vidyankur: Journal of Philosophical and Theological Studies. Jan-June 2021 XXIII/1 www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4718205 3-5.

Earlier studies showed that religious people use a coping mechanism that closely aligns with cognitive reappraisal by psychologists.

“For example, when somebody dies, a religious person may say, ‘OK, now they are with God,’ while someone who isn’t religious may say, ‘Well, at least they are not suffering anymore,’” Florin Dolcos said. In both cases, the individual finds comfort in framing the situation in a more positive light.

To determine if religious people rely on – and benefit from – reappraisal as an emotion-regulation strategy, the researchers recruited 203 participants with no clinical diagnoses of depression or anxiety. Fifty-seven of the study subjects also answered questions about their level of religiosity or spirituality.

The researchers asked them about their coping styles. “So, for religious coping, we asked if they try to find comfort in their religious or spiritual beliefs,” Hohl said. “We asked them how often they reappraise negative situations to find a more positive way of framing them or whether they suppress their emotions.”

The researchers also evaluated participants’ confidence in their ability to cope and asked them questions designed to measure their symptoms of depression and anxiety.

Hohl was looking for correlations between coping strategies, religious or nonreligious attitudes and practices, and levels of distress. She also conducted a mediation analysis to determine which practices specifically influenced outcomes like depression or anxiety.

“If we are just looking at the relationship between religious coping and lower anxiety, we don’t know exactly which

strategy is facilitating this positive outcome,” Sanda Dolcos said. “The mediation analysis helps us determine whether religious people are using reappraisal as an effective way of lessening their distress.”

The sought to find out individual’s confidence in their ability to handle crises – another factor that psychological studies have found is associated with less depression and anxiety – “facilitates the protecting role of religious coping against such symptoms of emotional distress,” Sanda Dolcos said. “We found that if people are using religious coping, then they also have decreased anxiety or depressive symptoms.”

Cognitive reappraisal and coping self-efficacy were contributing to those decreased symptoms of distress, she concluded. Hohl said. “It should also speak to clergy members or church leaders who can promote this kind of reappraisal to help parishioners make sense of the world and increase their resilience against stress.” “I hope this is an example of where religion and science can work together to maintain and increase well-being,” Florin Dolcos added.

Such collaboration between science and religion has been beneficial to both. So, all the articles in this volume deal with themes related to science and theology, reason and religion. It is hoped that a mature encounter will enhance the meaning and worth of human beings, especially during this pandemic.

The Editor

Reference

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. (2021, January 8). Religion, psychology share methods for reducing distress, study finds. Science Daily. Retrieved April 24, 2021 from www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2021/01/210108111046.htm